

THE FORMATION OF MEDICAL PERIPHRASES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7653286>

ELSEVIER

Received: 18-02-2023

Accepted: 18-02-2023

Published: 22-02-2023

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Abstract: The article discusses the factors of the formation of medical periphrases, including metaphor, metonymy, and synecdoche. Also, it is shown that medical periphrases can enter into a synonymous and homonymous relationship in terms of content and form.

Keywords: linguistics, medical periphrases, journalistic text, lexical and semantic meaning, languages of unrelated cultures, metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, comparative analysis.

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In the 50s of the 20th century in world linguistics, in particular, in Russian linguistics, I. Z. Ilyina (1954) [5, 24]; V. P. Utkina (1959) [16, 87] studied the role of periphrases among the methodological means that enrich and polish speech, their aspects associated with other linguistic phenomena and means. In addition, we note that the diverse nature of periphrasis has led to the emergence of many studies in world linguistics, and the definitions given to it are also different. In linguistics, interest in periphrases has increased since the 70s of the 20th century. In Russian linguistics, research by V.P. Grigoriev for the first time described it as a linguistic problem in terms of word-image-denotation relations as "one of the most striking, interesting, and promising ways to create poetic speech" [3, 104]. The studies of S.Y. Makarova contains valuable remarks on the artistic and expressive properties of periphrases, their place in the stylistic figures and tropes, and types of verbs [14, 55]. In particular, linguists were particularly interested in the interpretations aimed at revealing the nature of periphrasis in Y.D. Apresyan's article "Linguistic Means of Meaning and Rules of Periphrasis". That is, humanity (in the broadest sense) will be able to figuratively express ideas", writes the linguist.

Periphrases serve to enrich the speech, make it attractive, symbolic, and impressive, and strengthen the content of the address. Periphrases, as one of the important stylistic devices related to the speech process, give the speech grandeur, elation, and impressiveness, and at the same time, the speaker or writer takes a serious attitude to the speech and pays attention to each lexical unit. For one thing, to avoid simple words when naming the event, to give pathos to an unavoidable reality, famous writers and poets in English people, including Charles Dickens in

"David Copperfield", William Shakespeare in "Sonnet", Alexander Pope in "The Rape of the Lock", Oscar Wilde in "The Importance of Being Earnest" and S.T. Coleridge in "Kubla Khan" used periphrases with their skill [6, 144].

It is known that the transfer of word meaning occurs through several methods, such as metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, and simile. Among these methods, metaphor, metonymy, and synecdoche play an important role in the formation of medical periphrases [3, 1637]. According to the method of formation of periphrasis in English and Uzbek, the most common type of periphrasis is formed with the help of metaphor. Metaphor is the use of a lexeme to refer to things and events other than their specific expression, based on the similarity of things and events. Metaphorical units of periphrasis are often used in medical speech, in general, and in other functional styles of language [6, 143].

For example, Basil has a long history of use, being known as *the royal herb* in ancient Greece, and employed in various cultures not only for culinary but also medicinal and religious use (www.newworldencyclopedia.org). It is no secret that the basil plant is considered useful and healing in all folk medicine, which is why it is called *the royal herb*.

Another example: *High blood pressure is often called the silent killer because most people who have it don't have any symptoms* (Mayo Clinic health system, 2020); *High blood pressure, sometimes called the silent killer, is very common in older people and a major health problem* (Mayo Clinic health system, 2020); *The mutated virus is a ticking time bomb* (The Atlantic, 2020). In the above-mentioned first sentence, the blood pressure is given as *a silent killer*, and in the second sentence, a mutated virus is given as *a ticking time bomb* by metaphorical periphrasis.

In Uzbek: *Oshqovoq – sariq oltin* («Shifo-info», 2016. № 44); *Go'zallik, salomatlik va yoshlik ramzi – zaytun* (Mehrigiyo, 2018); *Yelbo'g'oz – yolg'on homiladorlik haqida bilamizmi?* (<https://qomus.info>); *TIA (Tranzistor ishemik ataka) – sezilmas xastalik* («Hamshira», 2016. № 6).

It should be noted that in the emergence of medical periphrases based on metaphors, not the similarity of form, but the similarity of color, a certain sign-property takes the leading place. So, this evidence of medical speech is periphrastic units formed by metaphorical means, and it shows that the formation of medical periphrasis in Uzbek and English is very productive based on metaphorical transfer.

The next place in the formation of medical periphrases is metonymy. Metonymy is the use of one representative for another representative based on the interdependence and relationship of expressions, which creates periphrasis. Medical periphrases formed based on metonymy also occupy an important place in the speech. For example, *The hospital was crowded with surgically interesting*

products of the fighting in Africa (I. Show). In this sentence, *surgically interesting products of the fighting in Africa* is a periphrasis formed based on metonymy and means *the wounded*. Another example, Western people called Democritus *the father of the atomic theory*, and Hippocrates *the father of modern medicine*, and his ideas with metonymic periphrases such as *the gift of knowledge*.

In Uzbek: *Kosmetolog – go'zallik yaratuvchi inson* («Shifo-info», 2019. №10); *Kasalliklarni (xususan, ichki kasalliklarni) to'g'ri aniqlashi, ularning qanday kechishlarini to'g'ri va aniq tasvirlab berganligi va bu sohadagi qator kashfiyotlari Ibn Sinoni hozirgi zamon terapiyasining asoschisi, deb atashga imkon beradi.* («Tib qonunlari» 1st Book, P.7) Syntactic devices show that metonymy is also characteristic of periphrasis, including medical periphrasis. Such a connection in figurative expressions is characterized by being figurative.

The next way is synecdoche, the representation of the part through the whole, and the whole through the part occupies a special place in the formation of periphrases. The occurrence of medical periphrases based on synecdoche is a minority. For example, *Oshqovoq ichidagi dorixona. Oshqovoq urug'ining qurt tozalovchi sifatini barcha biladi. Ammo shu bilan birga bu urug'ning foydalari ko'p.* («Darakchi», 2019, № 25)

In the last three years, the people of the whole world have gone through difficult trials. Unfortunately, the coronavirus has not spared the Uzbek people either. In such conditions, we observe that this process is expressed in the mass media with various periphrases. Here we can see that the single medical term "coronavirus" is represented by several periphrases: In English, it is possible to find synonyms of the periphrases such as coronavirus – *invisible enemy, year of pain, fear, and heartbreaking loss, threatens the life of the nation, deadly pandemic*.

In Uzbek, *Koronavirus – insoniyatning yangi dushmani.* («Darakchi", 2020, № 42); *Tojdor virus jannatmakon o'lkamizga xavf solmoqda.* (O'zA, 01.04.2020); *Agar biz bu xatarga beparvo, beg'am bo'lsak, minglab odamlarning sog'lig'i va taqdirini xavf ostiga qo'yamiz, vaziyatimiz yanayam og'irlashadi.* (From the address of Sh. Mirziyoev on July 17, 2020); *Faqat tezkor va muntazam safarbarlik, temir intizom, tibbiy madaniyat, yuksak onglilik bilangina biz bu ofatga qarshi kurasha olamiz.* (From the address of Sh. Mirziyoev on July 17, 2020)

We can also see the synonymy between medical periphrases in figurative expressions used in place of the unit "inoculation": *Vaktsinatsiya – viruslarga qarshi qalqon.* («Sug'diyona», 2018, № 40); *Emlanish – organizm va xastalik uchrashuvi.* («Doktor press», 2017, № 6)

It is known that AIDS is an acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, a disease caused by a virus belonging to the retrovirus group. Medical paraphrases, which are united around the concept of the AIDS unit, and enter into a synonymous

relationship, also occupy an important place. For example, *AIDS – 21st century plague*, the global number of people living with HIV has doubled in a decade to exceed 40 million for the first time. (Independent, November 2005); *AIDS is the late stage of HIV infection* that occurs when the body's immune system is badly damaged because of the virus. (Hiv.gov, June 2020); *Apart from being serious diseases in their own right, sexually transmitted diseases increase the risk of contracting or transmitting AIDS infection*. (NIH-HIVinfo, August 2021); *It is responsible for causing the breakdown of the human immune system, known as AIDS*. (Canadian Medical, July 2018).

In Uzbek, the synonymous line that unites around the concept of the AIDS unit is as follows: *OITS – hayot kushandasi*. («Shifo-info», 2011, № 47); *Ammo hayot go'zalliklarini bir lahzalik huzur-halovatga almashtirib, o'z hayotini zulmat qa'riga g'arq qilayotgan, nafaqat o'zlarini, balki hayotdan umidlari ko'p, begunoh kishilarni ham o'zlari bilan jarlikka tortib ketayotgan kasallik va u bilan kasallangan shaxslarning mavjudligi achinarlidir*. («Shifo-info», 2011, № 47); *Ha, bu o'sha yillar davomida kurashib kelayotganimiz, global muammoga aylanib ulgurgan OITS balosi*. («Shifo-info», 2011, № 47).

Although homonymy is not as important as synonymy among medical periphrases, we have seen that there are some examples. *Syphilis is a sexually transmitted disease that spread from person to person through sexual activity, including anal, vaginal, or oral sex*. (NIH-HIVinfo, August 2021); *Apart from being serious diseases in their own right, sexually transmitted diseases increase the risk of contracting or transmitting AIDS infection*. (NIH-HIVinfo, August 2021). In these examples, we observe that the periphrasis *sexually transmitted disease* is applied to diseases caused by two different viruses.

The following examples confirm the existence of lexical-semantic relations among medical periphrases in the Uzbek language: *Dizenteriya – yuvilmagan mevalar va iflos qo'llar kasalligi*. *Dizenteriyani iflos qo'llar kasalligi deyishadi*. *Sababi, gigiena qoidalariga rioya etmaslik, ko'chadan qaytgach yoki ish joyida qo'llarini yuvmay ovaqatlanish, kasallanish ehtimolini oshiradi*. («Darakchi», 2019, №16); *Gepatit A – kir qo'llar kasalligi*. («Darakchi», 2019, № 21).

In both of the examples given above, the figurative expression of the disease of dirty (dirty) hands, which means a disease caused by not washing hands, is used. The most important point for us is that the medical phrase describes two completely different diseases (the first is dysentery; the second is hepatitis A).

In short, figurative expressions, that is, periphrases, exist in the form of functional-semantic synonyms of words that arose due to the addressee's need to rename reality, the object. Figurative expressions, while avoiding repetition in the text, undoubtedly give aesthetic pleasure to the representatives of communication. Also, several ways such as metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, and synecdoche play an important role in the formation of medical periphrases.

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